

Materials selection for $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -based PCM thermal energy storage system

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the work carried out in 'SEHRENE' (Horizon Europe Project) to select suitable materials of construction for $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -based PCM (phase change material) thermal energy storage system. Commonly used construction materials, such as carbon steels, often have corrosion rates that limit their use in industrial PCMs. Metals that form passivating oxide films, such as Al, may give lower corrosion rates if fluxing of the oxide does not occur in the molten PCM. There have been suggestions to use Al alloy construction materials in PCM-based thermal energy storage (TES) systems where better heat transfer is essential, and carbon steel where structural integrity and cost-effective construction material is more suitable. This philosophy forms the core of the TES design in the above mentioned project. However, galvanic corrosion between the two dissimilar metals is a concern. To understand this further, carbon steel substrates were coated with Al, cut to expose Al-steel interface, and exposed to molten $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The galvanic corrosion performance was determined by examining the cross-sections of specimens post-exposure. The cross-sectional metallographic analysis revealed that corrosion was detectable. However, no significant effect was discernable. The experimental work demonstrated that $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ could be a potential PCM candidate for thermal energy storage system. The study also indicated coatings, such as thermally sprayed aluminum (TSA), could be considered for such applications to mitigate the corrosion issues based on the ease of application, availability, and cost.

Keywords: Thermally sprayed aluminum (TSA), Phase change materials, molten salt corrosion, galvanic corrosion

INTRODUCTION

Heat sources such as geothermal fluids have played a vital role in the renewable energy landscape for many years due to their weather-independent nature.¹⁻³ Heat sources also include industrial waste heat. The proportion of waste heat relative to energy consumption differs significantly across industrial sectors, averaging around 10%. The temperature of this heat ranges from 50°C to 1000°C, depending on the process.⁴ The European industrial sector accounts for about 25% of total energy consumption in Europe. This share of consumption varies widely, ranging from 15% in Cyprus to over 40% in Finland.⁵ Depending on the industrial sector, plants generating heat and/or handling heat during operation end up dissipating waste heat into the environment. EU, Canada, and USA have very high industrial waste heat potential in terms of recoverable heat. These countries have an annual industrial waste heat generation of 2.7EJ, 2.3EJ, and 1.3EJ, respectively.⁶ Turkey and Canada have an estimated 17.4% and 26.4% of their total annual energy consumption as industrial waste heat. This heat could possibly be used for processes such as drying, steaming, boiling, sterilizing, etc. Some of these options to use industrial waste heat utilization options are classified as passive system that utilizes energy only in the thermal form with temperature being either same or less than the industrial waste heat source. One such technique is the use of thermal energy storage (TES). TES is a key enabling technology for energy storage in the form of heat across all major thermal energy sources, including solar, geothermal, fossil, nuclear, biomass, and as stated earlier, waste heat. Although each thermal energy source has its own unique context, the key component is the use of a phase change material (PCM) offer a promising solution by utilizing latent heat during phase transitions, such as melting or solidification, in addition to the use of sensible heat. A wide range of materials are used for thermal energy storage (TES). These materials must have suitable thermo-physical properties, such as an appropriate melting point, high latent and specific heat, and good thermal conductivity. Other desirable traits include low supercooling, cost-effectiveness, availability, thermal and chemical stability, low volume change, non-toxicity, low vapor pressure, congruent melting, and low flammability.⁷⁻⁹ These PCMs can be either organic or inorganic compounds and, in addition to storing energy as heat, serve to stabilize thermal fluctuations resulting from changes in operational conditions.^{10,11} While water as a PCM has been used in steam engines for centuries, the operational range is limited by the phase change temperature and pressure.⁷ Therefore, finding a stable heat storage medium with excellent heat transfer properties and high-temperature stability remains a complex task.¹² Additionally, the compatibility of the PCM storage system's construction materials with the chosen PCM is crucial for operational safety and longevity.^{13,14} Whilst there are many options available in the market, high temperature molten inorganic salts have become the industry choice for PCMs due to their low vapor pressure, low toxicity, easy transportation, low reactivity in air and high operating temperature where high enthalpy heat source is available.¹¹⁻¹⁶ One notable PCM is the magnesium chloride salt.^{15,17} However, the use of such salts have raised concerns regarding degradation of materials.^{18,19} To address this issue and to ensure the long-term operation of PCM storage systems, protecting the most commonly used engineering alloy (carbon steel) with a suitable industrial coating presents a cost-effective solution.²⁰

Thermal spray technology, particularly the twin-wire arc spray (TWAS) process, stands out as a reliable and economical method for coating carbon steel.²¹⁻²³ TWAS process was selected to coat carbon steel specimens in a recent study involving the use of thermally sprayed aluminum (TSA).^{20,23} The work showed that TSA had the potential to mitigate corrosion of carbon steel in molten nitrate-nitrite salt. However, the research was conducted using nitrate-nitrite mixture at a different temperature. It is unclear if the presence of TSA would protect carbon steel from corrosion or that the presence of multi-material system could lead to accelerated galvanic corrosion of the more active component. In order to fill this knowledge gap, deliberate galvanic couples were introduced to the TSA-coated specimens, exposing the steel-TSA interface, and subsequently tested in a molten $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ salt environment. This paper provides an analysis of the corrosion performance of TSA coatings containing intentionally induced damage and exposed to molten magnesium chloride salt environment.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

Carbon steel (S355) was used as the substrate in this study. Specimens of dimensions 80mm×50mm×6mm were cut for thermal spraying. Prior to the thermal spray process, angular alumina (type NK36) at 100 psi was used to grit blast the substrates to Sa 2.5. Coatings were deposited from Al 1050 wire (01E) whose composition is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1
Chemical composition (nominal) of the wire and substrate used for specimen preparation

Material	Al (wt.%)	Mn (wt.%)	C (wt.%)	Cu (wt.%)	Fe (wt.%)
Substrate	-	1.40	0.14	0.03	Balance
Wire	99.5 min	0.05 max.	-	0.02 max.	0.40 max.

Thermal spray coating

TWAS coatings were prepared using a Metallisation 528 arc-spray system with 2.3mm diameter wires drawn continuously from two separate spools using a gun wire pull system. Table 2 summarizes the process parameters maintained throughout the coating deposition to obtain a nominal coating thickness of 0.3mm.

Table 2
Twin-wire arc spray process parameters

Wire Feed rate (m.min ⁻¹)	Spray Distance (mm)	Increment step (mm)	Traverse speed (m.s ⁻¹)	Voltage (V)	Current (A)
5.0	95.0	10.0	0.45	33.0	200

Sample preparation for corrosion tests

Once coated with TSA, the specimens were sectioned. The edges of the sectioned side of the samples were chamfered according to the ASTM G1 standard by grinding with P120 grit-size SiC abrasive paper. The samples were then thoroughly rinsed, first with deionized (DI) water and then with acetone, to eliminate any contaminants, followed by hot air drying. Two samples, measuring ~39 mm × 50 mm × 6 mm, were tested for repeatability. Before conducting the immersion test, the samples were photographed, measured, and weighed.

Corrosion testing

A flanged reactor equipped with a band heater was selected for the experimental trial. A total of 1.5 kg of MgCl₂·6H₂O salt in the solid state was placed in a 5 L flanged reactor. The reactor was heated to 130 ± 2 °C using a band heater wrapped around the reactor and a hot plate. A K-type thermocouple was used to maintain this temperature. Once the salt was fully molten, the samples, placed in a glass basket, were immersed into the molten salt. The thermocouple was positioned close to the samples to monitor the temperature during immersion, which lasted for 24 hours.

After the test, the glass baskets containing the samples were removed from the molten salt and the samples were rinsed thoroughly – first with DI water, followed by acetone – to remove any residual salt

from the surface. The samples were then photographed after exposure. For a visual representation of the experimental procedure, please refer to the schematic diagram in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Schematic showing the experimental programme

Characterization

The specimens coated with TSA were photographed both prior to and following testing. Microstructural analysis was performed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy dispersive x-ray (EDX) analyzer. The EDX analysis facilitated the identification of the constituent elements. Microscopic images were taken of both the specimen top surface and cross-section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Photographs of specimens

Figure 2 shows photographs of the test specimen, TSA-coated steel, both before (Figure 2a) and after exposure (Figure 2b) to a molten $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Noticeable changes in the coloration of the TSA is evident after the 24 hour exposure. The edge of the specimen had the steel exposed, but the photograph in Figure 2 does not show this face. It appears that the $\sim 130^\circ\text{C}$ exposure for 24 hours has caused some deterioration in the 'TSA,' however, the coating remained adhered to the steel substrate without any signs of disbondment.

Figure 2 Photographs of TSA coatings before (a) and after (b) testing

Macrograph of specimen

Figure 3 shows the micrograph of the thermal spray coating that was exposed to the molten salt environment. Thermal spray coatings tend to have porosity as a result of the deposition process.²⁴⁻²⁵ Some of the salient features on the TSA surface are visible in the image (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Optical macrograph of the TSA coating

The micrograph provides some evidence of impact of molten droplets. In the thermal spray process, the consumable is heated above its melting point, and these molten or semi-molten droplets, are propelled towards either the substrate or previously deposited particles by air (in this case) or nitrogen. Upon impact, the molten droplet spreads, cools, and takes on a 'pancake-shaped' configuration called 'splats'. The evidence of melt-solidification is evident in Figure 3. The overlap of splats lead to a network of pores in thermal spray coatings.²⁵ The nature of the pores observed in thermal spray coatings is influenced by various factors, including the consumable material, spray process parameters, and the type and temperature of the substrate.²⁴⁻²⁶

Thermal spray coatings typically exhibit three common types of pores: inter-splat, intra-splat, and globular pores. These pore types differ in shape, reflecting their origins. The coating surface also displays some roughness, primarily resulting from the grit blasting process, where abrasive particles, such as alumina, impact the substrate and create a rough texture, as well as from the spraying process itself. Minor variations in coating thickness are also observed, often due to the incremental steps of the spray gun as it follows a raster pattern during spray application. As molten or semi-molten droplets emanate from the spray gun, they form a conical "plume" of particles that impact and solidify on the substrate or previously

deposited layers, creating tracks and contributing to peaks and valleys across the surface. This peak-and-valley structure significantly adds to the coating's overall roughness as seen in Figure 3.

Another interesting feature is the absence of clear galvanic corrosion at the steel-TSA interface. It must be noted that the magnification in the image is not sufficient to clearly identify galvanic corrosion, however, any significant galvanic corrosion would have been discernable even at the magnification used. Some embedded grit can also be seen at the TSA-steel interface. This is not uncommon in thermal spray coatings where grit blasting has been carried out prior to spraying.

Micrographs of specimens after testing

The SEM micrograph and associated EDX pattern of the top surface of TSA coating after exposure to molten salt is shown in Figure 4. The EDX pattern of region 1 shows evidence of Al, O, Mg and C. The presence of Al is expected in TSA. Some O peak is not entirely unexpected as oxidation of Al leads to the formation of oxides of aluminum. The source of Cl and Mg is from the use of magnesium chloride salt for testing. Some of the salt may have remained after the test.

Figure 4 SEM micrograph of the surface of the TSA coating after testing (a) showing the EDX pattern of region 1 (b).

The SEM micrograph of the coating cross-section (Figure 5a) reveals common microstructural characteristics such as inter-splat boundaries, pores, and surface roughness. A closer examination of region 1, as shown in Figure 5b, and region 2 (Figure 5c) provides a detailed perspective on the morphology of the coating and coating-steel interface. The coating appears to be largely intact, displaying some signs of corrosion damage. Some evidence of oxide formation of TSA was seen in the EDX patterns (Figure 5d and 5e). The presence of 'O' in these regions along with the difference in contrast in the back scattered electron (BSE) image indicated the presence of oxides of Al. Furthermore, the interface between the coating and the substrate (that was exposed to molten salt) shows some evidence of corrosion. 'O' peaks were identified at the interface (Figure 5f). Although the width of such region only extended to ~5μm, the exposure was only for 24 hours. It is not clear if the galvanic interaction between TSA and steel is entirely responsible for this and also if the corrosion of TSA would continue at the same rate as a function of exposure time. It must be noted that the test was conducted for only 24 hours, so any inferences made regarding long-term performance based on this short-term test should be approached with caution.

The presence of any corrosion product generated during the test remains uncertain, as any such product could have been removed during the cleansing procedure with deionized water. The formation of water-soluble corrosion products, which were subsequently removed during the cleaning process, cannot be ruled out. Several elements found in the EDX patterns could have been incorporated during the metallographic sample preparation stage. However, the source of Mg and Cl is clearly the salt used in the test.

a)

b) magnified view of Region 1

c) magnified view of Region 2

d) EDX of location 1

e) EDX of location 2

f) EDX of location 3

Figure 5 SEM micrograph of the TSA coating-steel system after testing (a) showing the higher magnification images of regions 1 (b) and 2 (c), and the EDX patterns of locations 1 (d), 2 (e), and 3 (f).

Arc-sprayed aluminum coatings on steel, used in the current study, typically show adhesion values exceeding 20MPa.²⁶ The presence of significant contrast in the back scattered electron (BSE) image close to the surface of Al and close to the steel-TSA interface in Figure 5 is worth noting. As stated earlier, this indicated compositional variations linked to the formation of corrosion products. Fundamentally, the intensity of BSE image of an area/location is dependent on the atomic number of the elements composing the area/location. Heavier elements produce a higher backscattered electron (BSE) yield, resulting in more backscattering events. Consequently, BSE imaging can reveal compositional variations within the specimen, with heavier elements appearing brighter in the image. For example, Fe, being heavier than Al, yields more BSE and appears brighter. Based on the microstructural analysis of the specimen, it is

reasonable to conclude that corrosion of the coating was evident. However, to quantify the corrosion rate of the coating electrochemical monitoring, using techniques such as linear polarization resistance or electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, should be carried out. Further evaluation of Al-steel couples using tools such as zero resistance ammeter (ZRA) will allow better quantification of the galvanic effects in such systems.

CONCLUSION

In this research, thermally sprayed aluminum (TSA) coating was deposited on carbon steel substrate using twin-wire arc spray (TWAS), and defect /damage was created by sectioning the coated specimen to expose the steel substrate. The coated specimen containing exposed steel was tested in molten $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ at $\sim 130^\circ C$ for 24h. Post-test characterization was carried out of the top surface and cross-section using SEM/EDX. Corrosion was evident in the coating or the coating-substrate interface from the microstructural data. The coating remained adherent to the substrate after 24h of testing. The TSA close to the 'damage' or exposed steel did show signs of accelerated corrosion as evidenced from the SEM/EDX analysis that showed the presence of oxides of Al. Although corrosion of the coating was evident, quantitative information on the corrosion rate was not obtained in this study. Electrochemical monitoring using techniques such as polarization resistance or impedance spectroscopy in molten salt should be carried out to quantify the corrosion rate. Tools such as ZRA could also be used to quantify the galvanic effects in such systems.

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